

Interview with Animator and Illustrator Masashi Kudō at FicZone 2019

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The artist Masashi Kudō visited the city of Granada on the occasion of the FicZone + Granada Gaming + Meeple Factory 2019 event. The CoolJapan.es team took the opportunity to meet and interview Mr. Kudō. Best known for his work on the excellent anime adaptation of the renowned and long-running manga *Bleach* —which began airing in 2004— by author Tite Kubo, Kudō has built an extensive career in the animation industry. His work has been closely linked to well-known studios such as Arms and Studio Pierrot —founded in 1979 by former members of Tatsunoko Production and Osamu Tezuka’s Mushi Production—.

One of the most talented artists at the studio, he has contributed to *Bleach* by creating storyboards, directing several episodes, producing key animation frames and layouts, and even designing new characters for the anime, as well as developing colour palettes for characters that lacked them, all under the supervision and approval of Tite Kubo himself, with whom he maintains a cordial professional relationship.

However, his career extends far beyond *Bleach*. Kudō has contributed his talent to many other series, such as *Angelic Layer* (2003). His first series as a director was *Re-Kan!* (2015), based on the manga of the same name by Hinako Seta. He has also directed *Chain Chronicle: Haecceitas no Hikari* (2016), among others.

He has also worked on animated feature films such as *Macross Frontier: Sayonara no Tsubasa* (2011), one of the most highly regarded films in the *Macross* franchise, where he was responsible for key animation, and he also contributed in the same capacity to the 2007 film version of *Naruto Shippūden*. As we can see, all of these are productions of major international renown.

Interview with Masashi Kudō

Cool Japan: Good morning, Mr. Kudō. To begin, we would like to ask about the beginnings of your professional career. Did you always want to work in the animation industry? Is it something you discovered as a child?

Masashi Kudō: Yes, I have liked anime since I was a child. I also enjoyed drawing. I have been drawing since childhood, and I was always curious about animating drawings—seeing how a character moves, how I could bring movement to what I created. That is how my interest in animation began.

CJ: Your long-standing connection with Studio Pierrot, known for series such as *Naruto*, has been quite remarkable. What has that meant for you?

MK: That's true, I've worked a lot with them. Before Pierrot, I worked at studios such as Arms, known for series like *Elfen Lied* and *Ikkitsusen*—I also worked on the latter. I also worked for Artland, and on projects for Sunrise, such as those related to Sergeant Keroro.

During a period working as a freelance animator, Studio Pierrot contacted me. I believe that working freelance for several years was a very enriching experience, as it allowed me to learn how to work in a versatile way, benefiting from my time at different studios, each with its own working methods.

Pierrot tends to focus more on manga adaptations, whereas companies like Bandai often focus on mecha works such as the Gundam franchise, which are not necessarily based on manga or novels.

CJ: You have worked as an episode director, directed anime series such as *Re-Kan!*—based on the manga by Hinako Seta—and *Chain Chronicle: Haecceitas no Hikari*, among others. You also create storyboards, develop colour palettes, and design characters... Which of these roles do you feel most connected to?

MK: The most interesting role for me is that of director. As a director, you can oversee all aspects of creating an anime or animated film. You have a certain level of control over everything—how each section operates and how the project develops as a whole.

CJ: You have collaborated for years with Tite Kubo on adapting his most well-known work, *Bleach*, into anime. What can you tell us about that experience?

MK: *Bleach* is a very long series. I have been working on the franchise for a long time, and it has had a strong influence on me. Working for years alongside Mr. Kubo has also been very influential, both in terms of his character design approach and his working style. I gained a great deal of speed and versatility in my drawing through that experience.

Tite Kubo is especially known for creating very attractive and charismatic male characters, as well as a wide variety of female characters, many of them very “cute.” Even today, the agility I developed working with him on *Bleach* continues to help me greatly in my drawing.

Masashi Kudō, the interviewee, creating a signed illustration for our colleague Andrés Domenech Alcaide and the rest of the CoolJapan.es team

CJ: One of the most complex tasks in the animation industry is adapting one’s own visual style to that of another creator. In your case, you have even created new characters for *Bleach*. How difficult is it for you to design these characters so that they fit within the original author’s vision?

MK: When adapting from manga, as in the case of *Bleach* —a tremendously long series— as I mentioned before, what I have always tried to do is to highlight how excellent and incredibly well-crafted the original characters were, while at the same time remaining faithful to Tite Kubo’s original drawing style, and ensuring that the characters conveyed the same sense of dynamism and personality he gives them.

Kubo’s drawing style also evolved throughout the manga, as often happens with long-running series, since the artist naturally develops over time.

So I followed the evolution of the manga’s artwork and aimed to adapt my animation style accordingly. This has been the case up to the present day. It is a very complex process, but also a highly rewarding one.

CJ: You have also worked on animated feature films, such as *Macross Frontier: Sayonara no Tsubasa* (2011), where you created key animation, and the *Naruto Shippūden* film (2007). What differences do you find when working on a series compared to animated feature films?

MK: The main difference is related to quality—specifically, the level of finish the drawings must achieve. When working on a film, there is a much stronger emphasis on visual quality, which must be higher than in television series. You have to deliver something in a film that cannot be achieved in a series, both due to time and budget constraints.

More time is devoted to every aspect of a feature film. Every frame, every keyframe, is reviewed, and the animation is carefully checked at each stage —how each frame is drawn and how they work together. A clear example can be seen in productions like *Macross*, where we must draw and animate highly detailed mecha, often requiring an extremely high level of precision in many frames.

CJ: You also have experience in the video game industry, such as your work on the Rockman series—specifically the Battle Network subseries (Rockman EXE)—and the film *Rockman.EXE: Hikari to Yami no Program* (2005). What is your opinion of the video game industry, and are you interested in doing more work in this field?

MK: In video games, I have not done as much work, although I have participated in the Sakura Taisen series, where character design is handled by artists from the manga and anime world.

I am currently working on a project related to the Sakura Wars franchise, although I cannot reveal much more at the moment—the title had not yet been decided at the time of this interview. In this project, I am once again collaborating with Tite Kubo.

I can tell you that my work here differs slightly from anime. When working on a video game, the priority is to design characters in a way that makes it easier for the 3D team to convert them into models and animate them using three-dimensional tools. In essence, the work is quite similar, especially in character design, but with that key difference in mind.

CJ: Are you a traditional artist, or do you prefer digital media? What are your preferred materials and techniques when working?

MK: Digital tools and workflows are very practical. For me, they are the most immediate option, and I try to use them whenever possible.

CJ: Aside from your work on the upcoming Sakura Wars project, are you currently involved in any other projects?

MK: I cannot say much more, except that I am preparing a new project of my own, in which I will act as director, and I hope to be able to share more news soon.

[At the time of this interview, Kudō was working on *Sanrio Boys*, and later went on to direct *Terminator Zero* (2024), an anime produced by Production I.G for Netflix, based on the *Terminator* franchise created by James Cameron.]

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Masashi Kudō, in high spirits, alongside his interpreter for the event, Ken Yamaya, and our colleague Andrés, for whom he created the Rukia illustration shown in the image.

Sources

- **Interview conducted by:** Andrés Domenech Alcaide [CoolJapan.es] |
Interview interpreted by: Ken Yamaya
- **Photographs by:** FicZone press team

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